

of the total parent material was indica in the mid-1960's; 10 years later, 96 percent was indica. The use of japonicas and ponlais declined over the decade.

Fifty-seven percent of the total parents were hybrids in 1965-67, and 74 percent in 1974-75.

Thus, we conclude that by the mid-1970's the original stiff-strawed varieties were being phased out of the breeding programs as parents, but that they continued to live on through a wide range of progeny. Rice breeders have incorporated their best genetic traits into newer rices better suited to local conditions.

Objectives of rice breeders in India

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To determine the overall objectives of rice breeders, we interviewed rice breeders at 10 agricultural research centers in India. We compiled the genetic traits for which the breeders used each parent

in each of 46 randomly selected crosses made in 1974-75.

Yield potential was cited as a primary breeding objective for making 89 percent of the crosses; fertilizer response was a breeding objective of 80 percent; and resistance to lodging, of 80 percent (see figure). Semidwarfs were almost invariably used as genetic sources of these traits. Grain quality was an objective of 69 percent of the crosses. Seventy-three percent of the times that tall varieties were used, the breeders hoped to transfer a preferred type of grain into the progeny; semidwarfs were used only 49 percent of the time for that. We found that 82 percent of the semidwarfs used for grain quality were locally developed, further indicating that introduced semidwarfs were often crossed with local rices to develop high-yielding varieties with acceptable grain quality. Forty-three percent of the crosses involved resistance to at least one disease, and 37 percent involved insect resistance. Resistance to blast, bacterial blight, and tungro virus were the most frequent disease objectives. Brown planthopper and gall midge

resistance were the most common insect objectives. Drought tolerance was sought in 9% of the crosses; cold tolerance, in 9%; tolerance to waterlogged soils, in 7%; and tolerance to deep water, in 2%. Tall or intermediate-statured parents were used as donors for most of these traits.

Development and spread of high-yielding varieties of rice in Iran

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About 80 percent of Iran's 380,000 ha of rice is grown in the two Caspian littoral provinces of Gilan and Mazandaran, which have sub-Mediterranean (warm temperate) climates with humid summers and mild winters. The ricegrowing season is from mid-April to late September, during which the average maximum temperature is from 18° to 31°C and the minimum is from 8.2° to 20°C.

About 70 percent of the rice area is planted to long, fine-grained varieties of the Sadri type, such as Dumsiah, Dumzard, Dumsorkh, and Moosa Tarom. The Sadri varieties have very good cooking quality by Iranian standards: long, fine kernels that elongate considerably on boiling but do not tend to expand or burst. The cooked rice is tender and remains soft even if kept overnight. The remaining area is devoted to medium- and short-grained varieties known as the Champas. All are indicas and are tall, weak-stemmed, and leafy. Mutual shading and lodging are problems, particularly when the plants are fertilized. Mehr, Firooz, Dumzard 193, Moosa Tarom 110, and Dumsiah 81 are improved Sadri varieties developed by selection from local mixtures. They are not heavy yielders and are susceptible to blast disease. Some of the japonica varieties from Japan, Taiwan, Italy, Egypt, and other countries yielded from 7 to 9 t/ha in the International Rice Adaptation Trials in 1969, but they were acceptable to neither consumers nor farmers because they were short-grained, had poor cooking quality, and lacked seed dormancy (which is essential in Iran, where the harvest season generally coincides with the rainy season).

Increased yield potential was the major objective of rice breeders who made 46 randomly selected crosses in 1974-75. Fertilizer response and resistance to lodging also were important among their goals, as was improved grain quality. Ten agricultural experiment stations, India, 1975.

The high-yielding varieties developed at IRRI have so far failed to perform satisfactorily in northern Iran, probably because of the low temperatures. However, some selections of IR498 and IR533 have yielded from 5 to 6 t/ha. IR5 also performed comparatively better in southern Iran, and efforts are being made to introduce it into that area. Century Patna, an improved variety from the USA, was found to yield higher than local varieties in farmers' fields. It is tall but stiff-stemmed and yields about 5 t/ha. It has long and fine grains but its cooking quality is poor. Because it yields more and is attractive in the field, farmers in Mazandaran province grow it under the name Misbah. Its area is spreading from year to year. It now occupies about 40,000 ha in that province.

Amol #1 is a semidwarf high-yielding variety developed from a 1965 cross of Tarom Firooz Kande/TN1. Tarom Firooz Kande is a local, tall, low-yielding variety with good eating quality. It was released for cultivation in Mazandaran province in 1973. It has long, slender kernels with acceptable cooking quality and matures about 140 days after sowing. It is more suitable in warmer areas. Sterility is a problem under low temperature in Gilan province. A number of other short-statured advanced lines that are capable of yielding from 5 to 6 t/ha and possess acceptable cooking quality are being tested in yield trials.

A new source of resistance to several diseases and pests of rice

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Rice breeders are always looking for new sources of resistance to different diseases and insects so that they can incorporate polygenic resistance into new varieties. R-68-1 is a tall variety that was bred at the Central Rice Research Station,

Raipur, M.P., of Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University, by crossing Rikku, a Japanese variety, with R4 (Surmatia), a local indica variety. R-68-1 has shown resistant to moderately resistant reaction to bacterial blight and bacterial leaf streak under artificial inoculation tests at Raipur, and to leaf smut, false smut, *Sogatia*, gall fly, and

green leafhopper in field screening trials. It has been extensively used in the crossing program of this station. Several of its derivatives have shown resistant to moderately resistant reactions against different diseases and pests in testing by the National Breeding Nursery and the National Screening Nursery at different sites in India, including Raipur.

Some derivatives of crosses that involve R-68-1 as a parent and that show resistant reaction to different diseases and insects. Central Rice Research Station, Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University, Raipur, M. P., India.

Cross combination	Derivative	Diseases and insects ^a
R-68-1/CR-10-4050	R 2329	BB
	R 2330	BB, WH
	R 2331	BB, FS, WH
	R 2335	BB, FS
	R 2338	LS
	R 2341	BB
	R 2343	BB, FS
	R 2386	BB, RTV, Sh. B, WH
	R 2389	BB, BLS, FS, GLH
	783	St.B
	R6-2390	BB
	R6-2520	FS
	R6-2521	BPH
	R6-2522	BPH, FS
	R-68-1/TN1	R 2356
R 2357		WH
R 2358		BB, BLS, FS
R 2359		WH
R 2363		BB
R 2364		WH
R-68-1/Jaya	R 2325	BB
	R 2380	BB
	R 2381	BB, BLS, LS
	R 2384	GM, RTV
	R4-2517	BB, Blast, FS
	R4-2518	BB, Blast, FS
	R4-2519	BB, Blast, LS, FS
	R4-2528	BB, FS
	R4-2529	BB, FS, LS
	DGWG/R-68-1	R30-2549

^aBB = bacterial blight; BLS = bacterial leaf streak; LS = leaf smut; FS = false smut; RTV = rice tungro virus; Sh.B. = sheath blight; WH = white head; St.B = stem borer; GM = gall midge.